

Assessing the Effect of Communication Process on Employee's Performance in Selected Super Markets in Gombe Metropolis

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Abstract

Communication is considered an essential tool for achieving organizational performance and growth. This study assessed the effect of communication process on employee's performance in selected super markets operating in Gombe Metropolis. The study was achieved by assessing the relationship between horizontal form of communication and employee performance. A structured questionnaire was developed based on the literature review of the relevant topics and Total number of 208 respondents were made available for this descriptive survey. For analyzing the collected data, the researcher used the software package for statistical analysis SPSS and chi-square for testing hypotheses. The result of the findings indicates there is effective communication between the staff, all with an average of good or very good. This implies that communication in super markets is effective and will enhance the employee's performance. Also, the effectiveness of horizontal communication was found to be greatest due to high level of mutualism between staff of same rank or level.

Keywords: Communication, Employees performance, Horizontal Communication, Super markets.

1.0 Introduction

Employee performance, according to Jiang et al. (2020), describes the abilities and competencies of certain people inside a company. Under such circumstances, highly competent staff members frequently exhibit increased competence and commitment to their positions, leading to better staff performance than lower-skilled staff members. Under such circumstances, highly competent staff members frequently exhibit increased competence and commitment to their positions, leading to better staff performance than lower-skilled staff members.

When coworkers or bosses in the organization are doing a good job at what they do, employees' passion and commitment are usually increased. Employee performance is greatly improved by the way the company interacts with and speaks with its staff; this is because it provides a source of inspiration and the opportunity to learn new skills and perspectives (Jiang et al. 2020).

Communication inside an organization can occur horizontally, downwardly, and upwardly (Madhuri & Ramsheker). Through official channels, such as policy documents, rules, regulations, etc., top management (the highest position inside the organization) communicates with individuals or groups lower down the hierarchy. An organization's ability to behave effectively depends on its communication model. Utilize open communication between leaders and members in organizations to boost participation (Hsiung, 2012). As a result of inadequate business communications within an organization, it affects the overall trust of employees in both employee productivity and business unit effectiveness. Studies have shown that communication improves employee performance (Goris, 2007) and poor communication reduces the participation of employees in the organization.

In the corporate world, communication is essential to enhancing the general operation of many organizations. It makes collaboration between companies and their clients and between employers and workers easier (Stavros, 2020).

According to Kalogiannidis (2020), communications plays a critical role in both employee performance and the expansion of companies or organizations. For companies that aim to make money, communication is thought to be the primary factor driving growth or development. It's worth noting that business-related information holds little significance unless it is effectively conveyed to various stakeholders within an organization. Hence, communication in business can be seen as the comprehensive process of sharing business-related information among employees or between different stakeholders (Stavros, 2020). Since most of the fundamental planning, organization, leadership, and control of the management process cannot be carried out without effective communication, civilization is unlikely without the knowledge or contact (Heinrich, 2020).

One of the major factors affecting the performance of the supermarkets is the degree of using social media marketing (Borg et al., 2020). Employees are also faced with a change management process, problem solving and decision-making challenge where management makes decisions on sensitive matters which require sharing ideas and information or consulting all employees and management in the organization which in turn is affecting the employee's performance and the organization as a whole. This again ensures that members of an organization or institution are working towards a common goal and purpose. Most organizations have challenges and continue to find the most effective flows for communicating with their constituents.

Horizontal communication referred to as lateral communication. This form of communication occurs between people of the same level in the organization (Otoo, 2016). The absence of such a strategy or effective communication flows tends to under-utilize the expertise and vital information from the employees, which could be a critical input for formulating an effective communication strategy to reduce or eliminate apathy in performing their roles.

Therefore, this study investigates the role of horizontal communication on performance of some selected super markets in Gombe metropolis.

2.0 Literature Review

According to John Wenburg and William Wilmot, in their book "Communication Studies An Introduction to Communication "Stating that communication is an effort made by someone to obtain meaning. Communication is not always written and oral, communication can also be done using body language (Darwis et al., 2021). The most important thing about communication is not how we communicate or what media we communicate with, but how someone can understand the information conveyed by the sender of the message. As humans, we certainly will not be separated from communication (Darwis et al., 2021). Communication is very important to improve the smooth running of office activities. Below is a description of the importance of communication in the office. Establishing a feeling of unity and allegiance among: Subordinates and superiors, Subordinates within their teams; Managers and superiors; Employees with the workplace, Communication has the potential to amplify employees' enthusiasm and passion for their tasks, Communication has the potential to enhance employee morale and adherence to rules, it enables employees to gain a clear understanding of leadership-established policies, regulations, and provisions. It facilitates swift access to information required by employees, Communication can enhance employees' sense of accountability, It fosters mutual comprehension and regard among coworkers, It also encourages employees to cultivate a cooperative mindset, Communication serves as a tool for managing irrelevant information, functions as a collaborative tool for working jointly.

2.1 Concept of Horizontal Communication Flow

Horizontal communication occurs among peers in the institution. This type of communication is progressively usual with the levelling of the hierarchical structure and the introduction of matrix organizations (Greenberg and Baron, 2008). Thus, it is the transmission of information between people, divisions, departments or units within the same level of organizational hierarchy.

Figure 1. Horizontal communication pattern

Source: Florence (2015)

Robbins et al., (2010) and Tubbs and Moss, (2008) highlighted that this type of communication within an organization is a laudable channel for an efficient and effective transmission of information, which also facilitates synchronization among peers. In a research analysis by (Tubbs & Moss, 2008), some significant functions of the horizontal or flat communication were unveiled. This type of communication can help improve coordination between departments regarding task accomplishment; it also encourages effective implementation of upper level decisions the reason been that lower level members within department are allowed to coordinate closely with one another during the formulation of the decision made at the top; conflict resolution is mutually practiced among members in the same department without the engagement of management; and to end it, teamwork is facilitated when a project requires tasks from different people or from different department in order to intensify job satisfaction and motivation by creating more empowerment in communication.

Theorists in communication disclosed that horizontal communication makes communication more cordial in nature than what downwards and upwards communication does. It tends to be usually easier with fewer social barriers between members (Greenberg & Baron, 2008). Like with any other form of communication, there are some challenges or deficiency with horizontal communication. Periodically, when there are set targeted task for group members within or in other department to accomplish which mostly requires a demonstration of group loyalty. As a result of such activity, communication tends to freeze at a point within the departments there by creating and encouraging ineffective communication. It becomes very difficult for employees to perform their part of task well in an organization. In other words, it can be difficult to resolve conflicts among the members because of the flat or straight nature of command. As a matter of fact, the impact of such problems can negatively affect the growth of an organization.

By enabling employees to discuss work-related subjects, horizontal communication cultivates a collaborative atmosphere in the organization. This promotes efficiency and problem-solving and helps to foster meaningful interdepartmental cooperation. Furthermore, it encourages staff functions to be carried out smoothly without unnecessary bottlenecks (Bhasin, 2023).

Therefore, this shows that there exist relationship between the communication process and employees performance in the work place. In this regard, the study hypothesized that "Horizontal process of communication has a positive and significant effect on employee performance".

2.2 Employee Performance

The primary driver of growth and success inside a business is the input that workers provide on the job (Korkaew & Suthinee, 2012). Task performance and contextual performance are the two categories of employee performance that Rich et al. (2010) identified for organizational effectiveness. According to Borman and Motowidlo (1997), task performance is the term used to describe actions that are directly related to tasks that indirectly assist the organization's score technical processes. These actions have a direct bearing on the official incentive structure of the company. Conversely, individual efforts unrelated to their primary task functions are referred to as contextual performance (Werner, 2000). However, these behaviors are important because they shape the organizational, social, and psychological contexts serving as the critical catalyst for task activities and processes. Employee performance on various tasks must be closely coordinated for the organization to succeed (Macey & Schneider, 2008).

Depending on the type of organization, employees in that organization carry out a variety of tasks. According to Borman and Motowidlo (1997), their primary responsibilities include production, storage, manufacturing, transportation, marketing, purchasing, distribution, business promotion, finance and accounting, human resources, research, and public relations. All these activities are interrelated to achieve the targets. Employees must correctly complete these in order to provide their best effort on the work. This will have great impact on the total production and progress of the organization. People are encouraged to perform honestly and provide their best work by a variety of elements, including skills, training, motivation, dedication, welfare, management policies, fringe benefits, salary and packages, promotion, and communication (Korkaew & Suthinee, 2012). The importance of employees performance must be understood by the management and sincere efforts must be put in that direction.

2.3 Effect of Communication on Employee Performance

There is no denying the significance of communication for firms when it comes to their capacity to impact profitability, as demonstrated by mounting data connected to worker productivity (Muda et al. 2014). A corporation can achieve strong coordination across its teams or units through effective communication; in contrast, a lack of it can lead to issues with managing business operations or seriously harm relationships between individuals. According to Chen (2008), there is a suggestion that individuals involved in communication processes should possess both fundamental skills and abilities. Failure to do so may result in information not being understood appropriately. Additionally, managers' actions and the facilities available in organizations play a role in determining whether or not information is deemed acceptable before it is delivered accurately. Furthermore, as one of the crucial elements, the managers have been asked to learn the

feedback gained from the employees which probably affects their work motivation (Muda et al. 2014). This relates to the circumstances that are currently faced by the employees including the right time of delivering such information, thus, they may perform based on the messages they receive. In obtaining such a good performance, the managers must show the initiatives of developing and providing opportunities to learn new skills to their employees through the communication process. According to Beyerlein et al. (2003), management must integrate support systems into the strategic design to enable workers to voice their needs and grievances. Doing so will maintain an organization's efficiency and maximize its most valuable asset its people. Additionally, other research has examined the direct relationship between employee performance and communication openness (Dwyer, 2005). Furthermore, some research has focused on the relationship between employee performance and fellows' encouraging communication (Ducharme & Martin, 2000).

2.4 Theoretical Review

In assessing the effect of communication on employee performance in selected super markets in Gombe metropolis, two theories were found to be commonly used to explain the effect of communication on employee performance in the literature. These theories include system theory and human relations theory.

2.4.1 Systems Theory

The general system theory was originally proposed by Ludwig von Bertalanffy, a biologist in 1968 in his work, *General Systems Theory: Foundations, Development, Applications*, was sort to explain the relationship between parts and the whole of living organisms (Weckowicz, 2000). This sort provides a general analytical framework (perspective) for viewing an organization. Since then, the theory has been used in academic fields such as psychology, history and physiology. Studies conducted by theorists in management studies expose a digression from the classical and human relations model. According to Booth (1986) the systems theory has more valid and applicable stance in internal communication. This is because the systems approach recognizes the role that communication plays in facilitating efficient functioning between the various components of the organizations. In organizational communication research, some main components of the systems theory have been identified that informs how effective communication leads to employee performance namely; wholeness, hierarchical and feedback. In systems theory, the whole determines the character and functions of parts (Weckowicz,2002). Wholeness refers to the interdependence of the various elements that constitute the system. This means that individual parts of a system contribute to the existence of the organization.

Conferring to Miller (2009), the concept of an organizational structure indicates that the relations within an organism are systematized by order of hierarchy rules. In this regard, components the main systems are designed into subsystems, making up the whole system, which itself operates within a larger environment. Miller (2009), feedback enables decision makers in the organization to strategize to be on top of issues thereby building network relationships. Conferring to Salem (1999), the systems theory operates from primary principles of inter-relatedness and interdependence, it can be said that the same basic principles form the basis from which communication audit occurs. Super markets have a hierarchical structure with the various sections functioning as a whole structure and all the staff working towards a common goal. The systems theory is therefore appropriate for this study. In view of this, the researchers would determine the effectiveness of communication leading to employee productivity and to describe the communication systems at Super Markets. The Authority comprises different sections and in order to achieve organizational goals, these sections or departments need to work together in order to achieve these goals. This means that, there should be effective internal communication (horizontal communication, upward communication and downward communication) between the management and staff of super markets to attain these goals.

2.4.2 Human Relations Approach

Around the 1930s, Human-Relations Theory originated and introduced as a substitute perspective to the classical theory (Kreps, 1990). The theory originally was put to test by Mayo, Roethlisberger and Dickson's, which became known as the Hawthorne Studies (Roethlisberger & Dickson, 1939). The Hawthorne Studies brought to bear four major phases namely: the illumination studies, the relay assembly test room studies, the interview program, and the bank wiring room studies. The Human behaviour school of thought shifted from the prominence on output and work design to the interactions of individuals. Emphasis of the Human-Relations Approach dwells more on the needs of individuals in the organization, the employee's participation in decision-making and the opportunity to send and receive messages. Human Relations asserted that it is vital to determine the individual needs of organizational members and it is achieved within effective organization-worker communication.

According to Skinner, Essen and Mersham (2001), effective management communication can be best accessed through the use of communication audit. Essentially communication is fundamental in the work of human resources. The importance of the Human Relations Approach is that it highlights the role of workers and social factors in the effectiveness of internal communication and the issues such as leadership. In sum, the human relation approach deals with the interaction between management and employees, their motivation and influence on organizational events. This

throws more light on what management and employees ought to do to ensure effective internal communication. This approach will help the study to determine the usefulness of the various communications channels such as memos, circulars, telephone conversation, the use of Internet and face-to-face interaction.

Among the above theories, the study underpins system theory because it is the theory that provides a general analytical perspective for viewing an organization. It can be applicable also to the study because system theory has been used in academic fields such as psychology, history and physiology, and has more valid in internal communication, that is Horizontal communication. This is because the system approach recognizes the role that communication plays in facilitating efficient functioning between various components of the organization.

2.5 Empirical Review

Madhur and Ramshanker (2020) examines the association between three communication patterns i.e. Upward Communication, Downward Communication, Horizontal Communication and Job satisfaction of employees work in large scale industries in Pune. From this study researcher have tried to indicate a positive relationship between interpersonal communication and performance of employees. researchers have used primary sources to analyze the data gathered. A structured questionnaire was developed based on the literature review of the relevant topics. The research concludes that good interpersonal skills are always proved important for employees in making organizations successful and it affects different elements of organizational effectiveness.

Also, Gbarale and Leburu (2020) Investigate the relationship between vertical communication and employee performance within emerging economy public organizations. The study adopted the cross-sectional survey as the design for the study and utilized the questionnaire as the primary data collection tool. The findings showed that vertical communication significantly contributes towards employee performance as evidenced by outcomes such as employee effectiveness and efficiency.

Similarly, Kalogiannidis (2020) Sought to explore the impact of business communication on the performances of employees. Communication was conceptualized into horizontal, downward, and upward communication forms and their influence on employee performance was determined based on data from 110 participants who were employees of different banking institutions in Greece. The study confirmed that effective communication in any business entity has a great influence in employee performance. Business is encouraged to maintain a good flow of information across the organization to as to improve employee performances and business profitability in the long run.

Grunert, Haas, Imami and Miftari (2020) studied the effect of consumers' supermarket competence on information search and shopping outcomes in two Balkan cities, Albania and Kosovo this survey raises the question whether consumers have acquired corresponding competences. Findings showed that higher levels of competence lead to more information search and better shopping outcomes, but that information search in certain cases can also increase perceived risk and diminish pleasure and satisfaction.

In addition, Reza and Nugroho (2020) examined the influence of organizational communication and leadership factors on the performance of employee. Data analysis technique used in this research is descriptive statistical analysis with multiple regression analysis method Based on the results of research and discussion that has been done then it can be concluded as Organizational communication significant effect on employee performance a Government Organization.

Lingga, Broto, and Halim (2023) determine the Effect of Horizontal Communication, Vertical Communication and Diagonal Communication on Employee Morale at the North Rantau Sub-district Office, both partially and simultaneously. The analysis methods used are descriptive analysis methods, multiple linear regression analysis, and hypothesis testing, the test results of the Coefficient of determination (R²) can be seen that the Adjusted R square value of 0.458 or 45.8% shows that Horizontal Communication, Vertical Communication and Diagonal Communication against Employee Morale at the North Rantau Sub-district Office of 54.2%.

2.6 Conceptual Frame Work

The conceptual model in this research is made up of two variables on one hand is independent variable called Horizontal communication process which is item drown from literature e.g Madhur and Ramsheker (2020) while on the other hand is the dependent variable called employee performance also drown from literature e.g. Kalogiannidis (2020).

3.0 Methodology

The study adopted a survey design that involved using a questionnaire to collect data from the staff of the selected super markets. Employee performance was measured on 5-Point likert scale Data collected were sorted, grouped, into tables with the aid of Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS). The collected data were analyzed, interpreted and discussed.

Population of the Study

The population of this study are presented in Table 3.1, which is made up of selected super markets within Gombe Metropolis.

Sampling Size

Deducing from the computation in table 3.1 above, the entire population under study were found to be scanty, and therefore, the researcher absorbs the entire population elements in each super market cluster. This is in conformance with Sekaran (2003).

Table 3.1: Names of Registered Super Markets and Branches in Gombe Metropolis

Names of Registered super markets	Addresses	Number of Employees
San Hussain super market	Old Market Gombe	90
San Hussain super market	Dua plaza opposite Bauchi Park along Bauchi Road. Gombe	26
San Hussain super market	Dada Lesso Jekadafari Gombe	4
Nasara Mart super market	Adjacent to APC Gombe	30
Abu Shurhabil super market	Tumfure Gombe	4
Makay Super Market	Sabon Layi Gombe	35
Stop-Over	Tumfure Gombe	3
Kids street	Buhari estate Junction Gombe	6
Mini Mart	Federal low cost good luck ebele road	10
Total		208

Source: Ministry of Trade and Commerce (2023).

4.0 Result and Discussions

The demographic information shows a predominantly male and married respondent pool, with a significant concentration in the 26-40 years age range. The majority of respondents have a high school education and relatively short employment periods, with a larger proportion of junior staff compared to management and senior staff. This demographic profile provides a snapshot of the survey population, highlighting key characteristics that may influence the survey results.

The validity of the research was obtain using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) with the help of contact validity as the validity test for the study.

Internal consistency which is called Cronbach Alpha Analysis were used to test the reliability of the questionnaire. The coefficient of Cronbach alpha reliability test ranges from 0.00 to 1.00 with any value above 0.7 indicating that the research instrument is reliable.

Table 4.1: shows the assessments of horizontal communication on employee performance based on opinions of super markets staff. The table on "HORIZONTAL COMMUNICATION ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE" evaluates how communication among peers affects their performance. Each item in the survey assesses different aspects of horizontal communication, using a rating scale that includes Disagree (D), Moderately Agree (MA), Agree (A), Strongly Agree (SA), and an unlabeled fifth category, likely indicating the highest level of agreement. The table includes the frequency of responses for each rating, the mean score for each item, and in some cases, the standard deviation (SD).

Table 4.1 Horizontal Communication on Employee Performance

S/No	Question	Category	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Maintain good language with colleagues	Strongly Agree	41	19.7	1.90	0.533
		Agree	147	70.7		
		Moderately Agree	20	9.6		
		Disagree				
		Strongly Disagree				
2	Share knowledge with colleagues	Strongly Agree	9	4.3	2.27	0.536
		Agree	133	63.9		
		Moderately Agree	66	31.7		
		Disagree				
		Strongly Disagree				
3	Discuss job requirements with colleagues	Strongly Agree	41	19.7	1.89	0.528
		Agree	148	71.2		

S/No	Question	Category	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
		Moderately Agree	19	9.1		
		Disagree				
		Strongly Disagree				
4	Listen to advice from colleagues	Strongly Agree	16	7.7	2.43	0.712
		Agree	95	45.7		
		Moderately Agree	90	43.3		
		Disagree	5	2.4		
		Strongly Disagree	2	1.0		
5	Seek information from colleagues	Strongly Agree	20	9.6	2.14	0.602
		Agree	143	68.8		
		Moderately Agree	42	20.2		
		Disagree	2	1.0		
		Strongly Disagree	1	0.5		
6	Sharing information motivates performance	Strongly Agree	160	76.9	1.38	0.776
		Agree	24	11.5		
		Moderately Agree	20	9.6		
		Disagree	2	1.0		
		Strongly Disagree	2	1.0		

Maintaining Good Language with Colleagues

A vast majority of respondents, 70.7%, agreed that they maintain good language when communicating with colleagues, while 19.7% strongly agreed. Only 9.6% moderately agreed, with no respondents disagreeing or strongly disagreeing. The mean score of 1.90 suggests a strong consensus on the importance of respectful communication in the workplace. The standard deviation of 0.533 indicates low variability, meaning that most employees share this view. These findings highlight a positive work culture where professionalism and respect are upheld, fostering healthy workplace relationships. Organizations should continue promoting this culture by encouraging open and respectful communication, which enhances teamwork and overall productivity.

Sharing Knowledge with Colleagues

A significant proportion of employees, 63.9%, agreed that they actively share knowledge with their colleagues, while 4.3% strongly agreed. Additionally, 31.7% moderately agreed, with no responses indicating disagreement. The mean score of 2.27 suggests that while knowledge sharing is generally present, there is room for improvement in fostering a more collaborative environment. The standard deviation of 0.536 indicates relatively low variation in responses. Encouraging structured knowledge-sharing sessions, mentorship programs, and collaborative learning platforms could help enhance this practice, ensuring that employees actively exchange information to improve their skills and job performance.

Discussing Job Requirements with Colleagues

A majority of respondents, 71.2%, agreed that they discuss job requirements with their colleagues, while 19.7% strongly agreed. Meanwhile, 9.1% moderately agreed, with no responses indicating disagreement. The mean score of 1.89 suggests that discussing job expectations is a common practice among employees. The standard deviation of 0.528 shows minimal variation, indicating a shared perception. These findings suggest that employees rely on peer discussions for better clarity regarding their roles and responsibilities. Organizations should support this by fostering an environment where employees feel comfortable seeking and providing job-related insights, possibly through team discussions or peer coaching initiatives.

Listening to Advice from Colleagues

Less than half of the respondents, 45.7%, agreed that they listen to advice from their colleagues, while 7.7% strongly agreed. A significant proportion, 43.3%, moderately agreed, while a small percentage (2.4%) disagreed, and 1.0% strongly disagreed. The mean score of 2.43 indicates a slightly positive perception, but the high percentage of moderate agreement suggests that not all employees fully embrace advice from peers. The standard deviation of 0.712 suggests moderate variability in responses. To strengthen this aspect, organizations can promote a culture of collaboration by encouraging mentorship and constructive peer feedback, ensuring employees feel comfortable seeking and receiving advice from colleagues.

Seeking Information from Colleagues

A majority of employees, 68.8%, agreed that they seek information from colleagues, while 9.6% strongly agreed. Additionally, 20.2% moderately agreed, while only 1.0% disagreed and 0.5% strongly disagreed. The mean score of 2.14 suggests that information-seeking behavior is common, though not overwhelmingly strong. The standard deviation of 0.602 indicates moderate variation in responses. This suggests that while most employees rely on their peers for information, there may be barriers such as hesitation or a lack of clear communication channels. Encouraging a culture of knowledge-sharing through team collaboration, informal discussions, and accessible communication platforms could enhance this practice.

Sharing Information as a Motivational Factor for Performance

A large majority of respondents, 76.9%, strongly agreed that sharing information with colleagues motivates performance, while 11.5% agreed. Meanwhile, 9.6% moderately agreed, while only 1.0% disagreed and 1.0% strongly disagreed. The mean score of 1.38 suggests a very strong agreement with this statement, indicating that employees view knowledge sharing as a crucial driver of their performance. The standard deviation of 0.776 shows some variation in responses, but the overwhelmingly positive sentiment suggests that information-sharing initiatives should be further encouraged in the workplace. Organizations can reinforce this by creating structured forums for collaboration, rewarding employees who actively share knowledge, and promoting an open culture where employees feel encouraged to communicate freely.

Insights from Horizontal Communication on Employee Performance

The findings suggest that employees generally maintain respectful communication, actively discuss job-related matters, and seek advice and information from their peers. While knowledge sharing is prevalent, there is an opportunity to strengthen this practice further through structured collaboration initiatives. Additionally, the high level of agreement that sharing information improves performance indicates that fostering a knowledge-sharing culture could enhance overall workplace efficiency.

To build on these strengths, organizations can implement mentorship programs, team-based learning activities, and collaboration tools that facilitate seamless knowledge exchange. Encouraging peer recognition and fostering an open, communicative workplace environment can also enhance information-sharing behaviors, ultimately improving teamwork and job performance.

Overall, the survey results indicate that employees generally maintain good language when interacting with peers and find discussing job requirements with colleagues to be highly beneficial for their performance. Knowledge sharing and seeking essential information from peers are recognized as important, though there is room for improvement. Listening to advice from fellow employees is practiced moderately, suggesting an area for potential growth. The belief that information sharing motivates better performance is strongly held, emphasizing the importance of effective horizontal communication in enhancing employee performance.

Inferential Statistics on Horizontal Communication and Their effects on Employee Performance in Supermarkets in Gombe Metropolis.

Table 4.2: Chi-Square Tests on Horizontal Communication

Test Statistics	Chi-Square	df	Asymp. Sig.
Maintain good language with colleagues	133.683	2	0.000
Share knowledge with colleagues	111.125	2	0.000
Discuss job requirements with colleagues	137.375	2	0.000
Listen to advice from colleagues	210.510	4	0.000
Seek information from colleagues	335.702	4	0.000
Sharing information motivates performance	431.038	4	0.000

Source: SPSS output based on researcher's field survey data, 2025.

Hypothesis

H₀₁ (Null Hypothesis): Horizontal Communication has no significant effect on employee performance in some supermarkets in Gombe metropolis.

H_{A1} (Alternative Hypothesis): Horizontal Communication has significant effect on employee performance in some supermarkets in Gombe metropolis.

Level of Significance

The level of significance (α) is set at 5% (0.05).

Decision Rule

Reject the null hypothesis (H_{01}) if the p-value is less than alpha ($\alpha= 0.05$); otherwise, do not reject it.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

This study provides a nuanced understanding of how horizontal flow of communication affect employee performance in supermarkets. While it aligns with much of the existing literature, it also reveals important differences and new insights specific to the Nigerian retail sector. By addressing these aspects, the study contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of communications role in organizational performance.

The research affirms the influence of business communication on the overall job performance of employees within an organization. The distinct form of communication, particularly horizontal communication, significantly shape the extent of employee dedication to their roles. This underscores the substantial impact that horizontal form of communication has on both employee performance and the long-term growth of the organization. The study was conducted at registered super markets in Gombe State, Nigeria, involving a sample of 208 staff. The findings highlight the positive effect of horizontal communication on employee performance, which aligns with Madhur and Ramshanker (2020) and Lingga et al. (2023). Effective horizontal communication fosters teamwork and collaboration, leading to improved performance outcomes. However, the study by Grunert et al. (2020) found that increased information search due to high competence in communication could sometimes lead to decreased shopping pleasure and increased perceived risk. This suggests that while horizontal communication enhances collaboration, it must be managed carefully to avoid potential drawbacks. In our study, the positive impact of horizontal communication was consistent with overall performance improvements, indicating that the benefits of enhanced teamwork and information sharing outweigh any potential negative effects in the supermarket context.

The following recommendations are necessary to improve how communication affects employee's performance

1. Business entities are advised to maintain effective information dissemination throughout the organization in order to enhance horizontal communication among employee effectiveness and foster long-term business profitability.
2. It can be suggested that managers should aim to strike a balance between Horizontal communication and other determinants of employee performance. By doing so, management can identify the most influential factors contributing to organizational success and incorporate them into the strategies for achieving organizational goals.

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